

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF GRAPH SOFTWARE IN DEVELOPING DIGITAL SKILLS IN MATHEMATICS LESSONS

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Abstract

The article discusses the use of digital tools, especially the Graph program in mathematics classes and its contribution to the development of students' mathematical knowledge. Focusing on the topic of "Solving a quadratic equation graphically" visual analysis and solving methods of these equations are presented through the program.

Using the Graph program gives students the opportunity to both deepen their understanding of mathematical topics and develop their digital skills. This approach supports increasing academic achievement and digital literacy.

Keywords: math, Graph software, function, graph, application.

Introduction

The formation of digital skills in the modern era is one of the important priorities in the education system. The development of digital skills in students not only increases the level of preparation for their future working life but also provides an opportunity to increase the quality of education. The rapid development of information technologies necessitates changes in teaching methods and tools. The formation of digital skills is not only limited to information technology classes but also takes place in other subjects, especially mathematics classes. At this time, it is possible to develop both logical thinking skills and analytical abilities of students by using digital tools.

The development of digital skills is the foundation of educational rights. The "Education Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan" envisages the adaptation of students to the digital environment and the creation of an educational system that responds to technological development. Within this law, the use of modern digital tools by teachers, the integration of educational programs with technology, and the provision of digital skills to students are based on legal foundations [8].

The importance of using digital tools in mathematics is also reflected in international practices. The study and application of digital technologies within the framework of 21st-century skills are shown as an integral part of educational programs [5].

At the same time, the document "Development of Digital Skills" published by UNESCO in 2017 paid attention to the role of digital technologies in education and noted the importance of increasing the digital literacy of students [3].

Thus, the application of digital tools such as the Graph program [10] in mathematics classes is important in strengthening both students' mathematical

knowledge and digital skills. Graph software is an effective tool for constructing and analyzing graphs. Thanks to the use of the program, students turn theoretical knowledge into practical applications and gain deeper understanding through visual analysis. It develops their numerical analysis and problem-solving skills.

Research

"Equation" is one of the fundamental subjects of mathematics and helps to develop mathematical thinking in students. Solving equations graphically allows students to understand the graphing of functions, learn solutions visually, and show how mathematical concepts can be applied in real life.

In the 8th grade, "Algebra and functions" content line "2.1.1. Constructs a quadratic equation appropriate to a life situation. 2.2.2. Solves quadratic equations. 2.3.1. It expresses the time dependence of the path of a freely falling object in the form of a quadratic function" [4]. implementation of standards requires students to have the skills of research, graphing, and presentation of results [7].

The use of the Graph application program in the implementation of standards allows to analyze of the solution of equations on a wide level, an easier learning method creates positive motivation in students and opens the way to the formation of wider skills. The digital solution of equations strengthens students' ability to work with mathematical functions, develops their digital skills, and makes the process of constructing graphs more clearly visible [2].

Let's consider the method of solving the work related to the topic "Solving a quadratic equation graphically" [6] in the Graph 4.4.2 version of the program presented in the 8th grade "Mathematics" textbook.

Example: Solve the equations using the Graph 4.4.2 program [6].

$$1) -2x^2 - 2x + 4 = 0 \quad 2) 0,5x^2 + 4x + 6 = 0 \quad 3) -\frac{1}{3}x^2 - 2x + 9 = 0$$

After loading the Graph 4.4.2 application program [6] on the computer, its main window opens. From the

menu bar, the "Function" item is clicked with the mouse arrow. The "Insert function" sub-menu item that

opens is selected with the mouse arrow and a dialog window with this name opens on the screen. Functions are written in the "Function equation" field (the field in front of $f(x)$) in the programming language. In the dialog window, the graph display (description) type of the function, interval and step, color, thickness, marker type, color, size, and other parameters are selected. After that, as soon as the OK command button is pressed, the graphs are built in the automatic system.

1) Let's first write the equation $-2x^2 - 2x + 4 = 0$ as $-2x^2 = 2x - 4$. In the "Insert Function" dialog window, select "Standard function $y = f(x)$ " in the

"Function type" field, and write the function $y = -2x^2$ as $y = -2 * x ^ 2$ in the programming language in the "Function equation" field. It is necessary to select the interval and step for which the graph of the function will be constructed. Since $[-5; 5]$ is the standard function, you can leave the "Steps" field empty or write, for example, 500 steps. These parameters determine the accuracy and description of the graph. Then select additional parameters such as color, line thickness, and marker according to the parameters and build the graph in the automatic system (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Graphing the $y = -2x^2$ function in Graph 4.4.2

After selecting that the representation type of the function is standard in the same coordinate system, let's write the function $y = 2x - 4$ as $y = 2 * x - 4$ in the

programming language in the "Function equation" field. Interval, step, color, thickness of lines, marker according to parameters, etc. select and build the graph in the automatic system (Figure 2):

Figure 2. Graphing the $y = 2x - 4$ function in Graph 4.4.2

On the monitor, the graph of the $y = -2x^2$ function is depicted as a parabola, and the graph of the

$y = 2x - 4$ function is a straight line. The parabola and the straight line intersect at the points $A(-2; -8)$

and $B(1; -2)$, the value of the abscissa of their points of intersection is the root of the quadratic equation. The abscissas of the points of intersection are $x_1 = -2$ and

$x_2 = 1$. By checking, we make sure that the numbers -2 and 1 satisfy the given equation (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Solving the $-2x^2 - 2x + 4 = 0$ equation in Graph 4.4.2

2) Let's write the equation $0,5x^2 + 4x + 6 = 0$ in the form $0,5x^2 = -4x - 6$. Select the function "Standard function $y = f(x)$ " in the "Function type" sub-menu item of the "Function" item of the program, and write the function $y = 0,5x^2$ in the programming language: $f(x) = (0.5)x^2$ in the "Function equation" field of the "Insert function" sub-menu item. Since the $y = 0,5x^2$ function is a standard function, the graph can be drawn from negative infinity to positive infinity. Therefore, we can leave one or both of the "From" and "To" indicators empty. Step, color, thickness of lines, marker according to parameters, etc. select and build the graph in the automatic system. After selecting the

display type of the function in the same coordinate system, we write the function $y = -4x - 6$ as $f(x) = -4 * x - 6$ in the programming language in the "Function equation" field. Set the graph in the automatic system by selecting other parameters accordingly (Figure 4).

The graph of the function $y = 0,5x^2$ is a parabola and the graph of the function $y = -4x - 6$ is a straight line that intersects at points $A(-6; 18)$ and $B(-2; 2)$. The abscissas of the points of intersection are $x_1 = -6$ and $x_2 = -2$. By checking, we make sure that the numbers -6 and -2 satisfy the given equation.

Figure 4. Solving the $0,5x^2 + 4x + 6 = 0$ equation in Graph 4.4.2

3) Let's write the equation $-\frac{1}{3}x^2 - 2x + 9 = 0$ in the form $-\frac{1}{3}x^2 = 2x - 9$. Then, alternately on the coordinate plane, in the "Function equation" field of the "Insert function" sub-menu of the "Function" item, write the functions $y = -\frac{1}{3}x^2$ and $y = 2x - 9$ in the programming language: $f(x) = (-1/3)x^2$ and $f(x) = 2*x - 9$. Since the coefficient of x^2 in the

$y = -\frac{1}{3}x^2$ function is $-\frac{1}{3}$, the graph of the function will be an expanded parabola. Therefore, we mark the interval where the graphs will be made as $[-15; 15]$. For each function, you can set the step, graphic image type, color, thickness of lines, marker according to parameters, etc. select and plot the graphs in the automatic system (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Solving the $-\frac{1}{3}x^2 - 2x + 9 = 0$ equation in Graph 4.4.2

The parabola and the straight line intersect at points $A(-9; -27)$ and $B(3; -3)$. The abscissas of the points of intersection are -9 and 3 . So -9 and 3 are solutions of the equation.

Thus, we got acquainted with the solution of the given quadratic equations in the Graph 4.4.2 software.

The method of solving quadratic equations in the Graph software

Quadratic equations are one of the fundamental topics of mathematics, and the process of solving them helps students develop logical thinking, visual analysis, and problem-solving skills. Solving quadratic equations graphically shows students the graphical representation of functions, solutions to equations, and real-life applications. Using digital tools, especially Graph software, is an effective tool for this process.

Steps for solving quadratic equations in Graph 4.4.2:

1. Preparation of the program:

- After the Graph 4.4.2 software is downloaded on the computer, activate the software.
- In the main window that opens, all the tools for creating graphs are available. Select the "Function" item from the menu bar of the program.

2. Writing the function in programming language

- Open the "Function" menu and select the "Insert Function" submenu.

- In the opened "Insert Function" dialog window, select "Standard function $y = f(x)$ " in the "Function type" field.

- Functions are written in the programming language to plot quadratic equations in the "Function equation" field.

3. Adjusting the parameters of the function

- It is necessary to define additional parameters such as interval, step, line color, thickness of the graph and markers.

- Colors and marker settings are adjusted to make the graph clearer. After setting all the parameters, by pressing the "OK" button, the graph will automatically appear on the screen.

4. Adding other functions:

- If it is required to find the point of intersection of two functions to solve the equation graphically, then the second function should be added.

- Open the "Insert Function" window again and insert the new function.

- Adjust the settings for this function as well.

5. Construction of the graphs:

- After entering the appropriate settings for each function, click the "OK" button.

- The program will automatically plot the graphs based on the selected parameters.

- The graphs of the parabola and the straight line, as well as the intersection points, will appear on the monitor screen.

6. Solving the equation:

- You can find the solution of the equation at the points of intersection of the graphs of the functions.

- In solving a quadratic equation graphically, the coordinates of the intersection points on the abscissa axis are the solution of the quadratic equation.

7. Final inspection and analysis:

- You can confirm the correctness of the solutions of the quadratic equation by checking the points of intersection. That is, the accuracy can be checked by inserting the found abscissas into the equation.

8. Summarizing the results:

- Thus, the solution of the equation was visually presented graphically and the roots of the equation were determined by finding the points of intersection. Graph software is an effective tool for developing students' mathematical and digital skills, as it provides the ability to accurately construct and solve graphs in a short amount of time.

Conclusions

Solving quadratic equations using Graph software provides students with a visual and hands-on learning experience. This approach concretizes the abstract understanding of quadratic equations with realistic graphical representations and develops students' logical thinking and analysis skills. By graphing two functions and identifying their points of intersection, solving quadratic equations becomes clearer and easier to understand. This process allows determining the roots of an equation graphically and allows students to follow the mathematical analysis step by step.

Graph software allows students to visually analyze each step as they solve math problems. Students not only understand solving equations more intuitively but also develop their digital skills through this program. Such an approach strengthens mathematical knowledge and forms habits of using modern technologies.

The application of the Graph program creates a more interactive, interesting, and motivating learning environment for students, unlike traditional methods.

This methodology not only increases the ability of students to solve mathematical problems but also develops the understanding of mathematical applications in real life.

Thus, Graph software is a tool that plays an important role in developing both mathematical and digital skills.

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